

Collecting Strike Data from Historical Newspapers (19th Century): A Digital Workflow

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The epistemological revolution spearheaded by Digital Humanists emerges at the tail end of a global wave of workers' mobilization that originated in the second half of the 19th century. This historical junction begs the question, if and how the new toolbox of a Digital Historian can contribute to the incipient new global history of collective labor action (Linden 2012).

To that end, I create and implement a workflow for the retrieval and annotation of text relevant for the study of strikes from three major collections of digitized German historical newspapers. To the growing Digital History literature concerned with the exploitation of large collections of digitized newspapers, this project contributes a proof of concept for the suggested workflow, an in-depth quality review of a selection of newspapers from three major German digital collections, a re-OCR pipeline and a segmentation approach to separate news reports. To the historiography of strikes in the first two decades of the German Empire, it contributes a novel data resource and a first assessment of the coverage of domestic labor conflicts in major newspapers.

Data

The core corpus consists of 42,000 daily issues (1870-1890) of six newspapers selected from the three largest collections of retrodigitized historical German newspapers for the late nineteenth century (*DigiPress*, *ZEFYS* and *zeitpunkt.NRW*). The selection of newspaper titles follows existing newspaper-based studies of social unrest in the 19th century (Tilly 1970) and includes two major interregional newspapers (*Kölnische Zeitung* and *Augsburger Allgemeine Zeitung*) and four regional newspapers published in Berlin and Bavaria. Secondary data sources are existing microdata on labor conflicts in the German Empire.

Workflow

Figure 1: Workflow

The workflow consists of three steps: First, I create a subcorpus of candidate newspaper pages by identifying relevant historical keywords (Oberbichler / Pfanzelter 2021, Pfanzelter et al. 2021) in a bottom-up manner using a statistical approach (TF/IDF) (Zervanou et al. 2014) and a novel ground truth dataset of newspaper articles collected based on source references in existing quantitative sources. To increase the accuracy of the corpus, I identify false positives with a text classifier trained on a tagged set of 2000 random sentences embedded using a *FastText* model (Ehrmann et al. 2020) with subword features (F-score = 0.91).

Figure 2: Comparing Provided OCR with Calamari-OCR

In a second step, I implement a re-OCR pipeline to improve the quality of the layout and text data provided by the archives using *sbb-binarize*, ¹*Eynollah*² and *Calamari-OCR* (Wick et al. 2018) with pre-trained models (Figure 2).³ Evaluating the results with a dictionary-based approach (Strien et al. 2020) shows that the mean OCR quality of the entire corpus was improved by 1.2%. Unlike the only moderate improvement in character recognition, the re-OCR pipeline substantially improves the layout and reading order recognition. A review of a random sample yields a considerably reduced share of pages with omitted lines (1% compared to 15% in the provided OLR) or an incorrect reading order (15% instead of 58%). To meet the challenge of missing article segmentation, I implement a line-based classifier trained on the visual and textual

features of an annotated set of 256 pages that performs well across the selected newspapers (F-score: 0.97, Figure 3).

Figure 3: From Regions (left) to Articles (right)

Ultimately, I annotate a sample of the resulting subcorpus of just shy of 21,000 relevant newspaper articles using *INCEpTION* (Klie et al. 2018) (Figure 4). On the document level I annotate whether or not a given article is a false positive and whether it mentions a past or ongoing event of collective labor action. Relying on *INCEpTION*'s built-in learning recommender systems and *SPARQL* query capabilities, I annotate places and occupations mentioned in the context of a conflict event and link them to their corresponding URIs: *Wikidata* for places and *HISCO* for occupations (Leeuwen et al. 2002).

Figure 4: Annotation in INCEpTION

Results for Studies of Labor Conflicts

For the years 1871-1875 I annotated the entire subcorpus of relevant articles and mapped the reports to the most comprehensive existing knowledge base of strikes in the early German Empire (Machtan 1984). Remarkably, only 10% of all the known strikes are mentioned in the selected newspapers, that exhibit a reporting bias based on event intensity as well as a sensitivity bias (Snyder / Kelly 1977) in favor of core economic sectors. These results suggest that strike data derived from the reporting of several major daily newspapers is likely to dramatically underestimate the ac-

tual number of events that took place. This provides an important benchmark for quantitative historical studies of protest and strikes and emphasizes the importance of including a broad range of smaller newspapers and other sources beyond the common approach of relying on small selections of major newspapers. The resulting dataset of annotated strike articles provides a promising starting point for further research into the coverage of strikes by newspapers, ideally using a broader corpus including local newspapers.

Notes

1. github.com/qurator-spk/sbb_binarization
2. github.com/qurator-spk/eynollah
3. KZT: Kölnische Zeitung, NAZ: Norddeutsche Allgemeine Zeitung, BT: Berliner Tageblatt, WS: Wendelstein, RZ: Rosenheimer Zeitung, AZ: Augsburgener Allgemeine Zeitung

Bibliography

Ehrmann, M. / Romanello, M. / Flückiger, A. / Clematide, S. (2020): "Extended Overview of CLEF HIPE 2020: Named Entity Processing on Historical Newspapers" in: Working Notes of CLEF 2020 – Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2696. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4117566.

Klie, Jan-Christoph / Bugert, Michael / Boulosa, Beto / Eckart de Castilho, Richard / Gurevych, Iryna (2018): "The INCEpTION Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation", in: Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations: 5-9

Leeuwen, Marco H. D van / Maas, Ineke / Miles, Andrew / Edvinsson, Sören (2002): *HISCO: historical international standard classification of occupations*. Leuven: Leuven university Press.

Linden, Marcel van der (2012): "The Promise and Challenges of Global Labor History", in: *International Labor and Working-Class History* 82: 57-76.

Machtan, Lothar (1984): *Streiks und Aussperrungen im Deutschen Kaiserreich: eine sozialgeschichtliche Dokumentation für die Jahre 1871 bis 1875*. Berlin: Colloquium Verlag.

Oberbichler, Sarah / Pfanzelter, Eva (2021): "Topic-Specific Corpus Building: A Step towards a Representative Newspaper Corpus on the Topic of Return Migration Using Text Mining Methods", in: *Journal of Digital History*, 1 <https://journalofdigitalhistory.org/en/article/4yxHGiqXYRbX> [01.05.2023].

Pfanzelter, Eva / Oberbichler, Sarah / Marjanen, Jani / Langlas, Pierre-Carl / Hechl, Stefan (2021): "Digital Interfaces of Historical Newspapers: Opportunities, Restrictions and Recommendations", in: *Journal of Data Mining & Digital Humanities*, 6121. DOI: 10.46298/jdmdh.6121.

Snyder, David / Kelly, William R. (1977): "Conflict Intensity, Sensitivity and the Validity of Newspaper Data", in: *American Sociological Review* 42, 1: 105. DOI:10.2307/2117734.

Strien, Daniel van / Beelen, Kaspar / Coll Ardanuy, Mariona / Hosseini, Kasra / McGillivray, Barbara / Colavizza, Giovanni (2020): "Assessing the Impact of OCR Quality on Downstream NLP Tasks", Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence: Valletta, Malta, February 22-24, 2020, 484-496. DOI: 10.5220/0009169004840496

Tilly, Richard (1970): “Popular Disorders in Nineteenth-Century Germany: A Preliminary Survey”, in: *Journal of Social History* 4, 1: 1-40.

Wick, Christoph / Reul, Christian / Puppe, Frank (2018): “Calamari – A High-Performance Tensorflow-based Deep Learning Package for Optical Character Recognition”, ArXiv. DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2004.1219

Zervanou, Kalliopi / Düring, Marten / Hendrickx, Iris / Bosch, Antal van den (2014): “Documenting Social Unrest: Detecting Strikes in Historical Daily Newspapers”, in: Nadamoto, A., Jatowt, A., Wierzbicki, A., Leidner, J.L. (eds.): *Social Informatics. SocInfo 2013. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 8359. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.